

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D2.6 Grant data publication inventory_M20

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Lead Beneficiary: VLIZ

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
eMOF	Extended Measurement Or Fact
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
DwC	Darwin Core (standard which facilitates the sharing of information about biological diversity)
DwC-A	Darwin Core Archive
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit

Keywords

Marine biodiversity data, monitoring data, FSTP grants, open call, EMODnet Biology, Digital Twin of the Ocean, data publication

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Despite significant advancements in Europe to collect, harmonise, and make available data on marine biodiversity, a large portion of data remains unavailable or inaccessible. This type of data is referred to as "sleeping data." To activate these sleeping data, two calls for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data are organised. The grants awarded through these calls enable establishing workflows and procedures that promote and facilitate the sharing of critical missing marine biodiversity data, and ultimately facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion of previously inaccessible data into the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) through publication in EMODnet Biology. Projects awarded a grant in the first round ran from March 1st 2024 until February 28th 2025. This deliverable provides an overview of the datasets published thanks to these grants. A total of 29 datasets, representing more than two million occurrence records, were published through the support of this first round of DTO-BioFlow FSTP (Financial Support to Third Parties) grants. The published datasets cover a wide array of methods such as citizen science observations, AI-assisted imaging and net trawling, focusing on a variety of organisms, from cetaceans to plankton, being collected from different regions, ranging from the Arctic Ocean to the Mediterranean Sea to the Azores and the South Atlantic Ocean, covering a wide temporal range, from 1920 to 2024. Through the pipelines established during the projects, we can expect these data flows to continue contributing data in the future. Therefore, the descriptions of the datasets in this report are a reflection of the current situation, but the number of records / datasets powered through the work done during these grants can be expected to only keep growing, generating a sustained data flow towards the DTO.

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1. Introduction

Despite significant advancements in Europe to collect, harmonise, and make available data on marine biodiversity, a large portion of data remains unavailable or inaccessible. This type of data is referred to as "sleeping data." To activate these sleeping data, two calls for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data are organised in the course of the DTO-BioFlow project. The grants awarded through these calls enable establishing workflows and procedures that promote and facilitate the sharing of critical missing marine biodiversity data, and ultimately facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion of previously inaccessible data into the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) through publication in EMODnet Biology. The first call was open for applications from October 31st 2023 to January 17th 2024 (more details about the launch, scope and conditions of the first call can be found in deliverable "D2.4 Call for data grants_M2"). A total of nine projects were selected to receive a grant. The selected projects ran from March 1st 2024 until February 28th 2025. This deliverable provides an overview of the 29 datasets currently published thanks to the grants awarded in the first round.

2. Overview of datasets per FSTP project

2.1. Pipeline for biodiversity data from the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) to the OBIS network and EMODnet.

2.1.1. General information

Table 1 – General information on "Pipeline for biodiversity data from the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) to the OBIS network and EMODnet".

Organisation	National Oceanography Centre
Data description	Biodiversity data of the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC)
Budget	€59,865.40

2.1.2. Datasets

2.1.2.1. Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) biodiversity data

Table 2 – Dataset summary of "Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT12 - Microzooplankton abundance and biomass (optical microscopy) (CTD bottles)".

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT12 - Microzooplankton abundance and biomass (optical microscopy) (CTD bottles)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1000633_amt12_microzooplankton_abundance_biomass_opticalmicroscopy_ctd
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8784
Data description	This dataset contains microzooplankton abundance and biomass data from CTD bottle samples collected during the Atlantic Meridional Transect 12 (AMT12) cruise in the Atlantic Ocean between Port Stanley, Falkland Islands, and Grimsby, United Kingdom, in May-June 2003. The data contribute to the AMT project and were collected by scientists from the Plymouth Marine Laboratory.

Number of occurrence records	315
Number of event records	68
Number of eMOF records	1,264
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2003-05-17 / 2003-06-12

Table 3 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT13 - Microzooplankton abundance and biomass (optical microscopy) (CTD bottles)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT13 - Microzooplankton abundance and biomass (optical microscopy) (CTD bottles)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1000634_amt13_microzooplankton_abundance_biomass_opticalmicroscopy_uvradiation_ctd
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8785
Data description	This dataset contains microzooplankton abundance and biomass, and UV radiation experiments data from CTD bottle samples collected during the AMT13 cruise in the Atlantic Ocean between the UK and the Falklands, in September-October 2003. The data were collected by scientists from the Plymouth Marine Laboratory and contribute to the AMT project.
Number of occurrence records	531
Number of event records	109
Number of eMOF records	2,134
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2003-09-14 / 2003-10-10

Table 4 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT13 Microzooplankton (nauplii and copepodites) and mesozooplankton taxonomy and abundance (Net Hauls)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT13 Microzooplankton (nauplii and copepodites) and mesozooplankton taxonomy and abundance (Net Hauls)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1000092_amt13_microzooplankton_mesozooplankton_taxonomyabundance_net
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8787
Data description	This dataset contains microzooplankton (nauplii and copepodites) and mesozooplankton taxonomy and abundance, ingestion rates, and nauplii gut evacuation rates data from net haul samples collected during the AMT13 cruise in the Atlantic Ocean between the UK and the Falkland Islands, in September-October 2003. To estimate zooplankton abundance, vertical net samples were taken from 200 m to the surface with a WP-2 net, equipped with filtering cod-ends, during night stations (between 00:30 and 4:30 h local time). The pore mesh net was 53 µm and 30 µm for the filtering cod-ends. Tows were performed at low speed (0.5 m/s). The net was not equipped with a flow-meter, so to calculate the volume filtered the diameter of the net (27 cm) was used (volume filtered: 11.45 m ³) for each cast. Samples were screened through 1000, 500, 200 and 30 µm meshes, put in 250 ml

	bottles and fixed with 4% buffered formaldehyde. In the laboratory, abundance of main taxonomic groups of metazooplankton was determined under a stereomicroscope. Ingestion rate was calculated using the gut fluorescence method (Mackas and Bohrer, 1976). The data were collected by scientists from the University of Oviedo Department of Organism and Systems Biology.
Number of occurrence records	624
Number of event records	25
Number of eMOF records	4,019
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2003-09-10 / 2003-10-14

Table 5 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT15 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT15 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=amt15_coccolithophore_composition_light_microscopy_ctd_bottles
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8789
Data description	This dataset contains coccolithophore abundance data from CTD bottle samples collected during the AMT15 cruise in the Atlantic Ocean between the United Kingdom and Cape Town, South Africa in September–October 2004. Bottle samples were collected at six light depths (i.e. at different PAR levels) from the pre-dawn (between approximately 03:00 - 04:30 local time) and noon CTD casts. Microscope enumeration of coccolithophores and coccoliths was performed by filtering a 100 - 500 milliliters water sample through a Millipore HA filter, which was then rinsed with borate buffer, and frozen in a petri dish until counted. The filter was placed on a glass microscope slide, and a 60 degrees Celsius Canada Balsam was placed on top of the filter, followed by a cover slip. The clarified filter was examined for birefringent and plated coccolithophore counts, with an Olympus BH2 microscope equipped with polarisation optics. For statistical reasons, 200 coccoliths or cells were counted from each sample, when available. These data were collected for the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project by scientists from the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences.
Number of occurrence records	569
Number of event records	356
Number of eMOF records	1,713
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2004-09-17 / 2004-10-29

Table 6 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT15 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (surface underway)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT15 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (surface underway)
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IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=atlantic_meridional_transect_amt15_coccolithophore_composition-light_microscopy_surface_underway
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8791
Data description	This dataset contains coccolithophore abundance data from surface underway samples collected during the AMT15 cruise in the Atlantic between the United Kingdom and Cape Town, South Africa in September-October 2004. Surface samples were collected approximately every 3 to 6 hours from the non-toxic water supply. Microscope enumeration of coccolithophores and coccoliths was performed by filtering a 100 - 500 milliliters water sample through a Millipore HA filter, which was then rinsed with borate buffer, and frozen in a petri dish until counted. The filter was placed on a glass microscope slide, and a 60 degrees Celsius Canada Balsam was placed on top of the filter, followed by a cover slip. The clarified filter was examined for birefringent and plated coccolithophore counts, with an Olympus BH2 microscope equipped with polarisation optics. For statistical reasons, 200 coccoliths or cells were counted from each sample, when available. These data were collected for the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project by scientists from the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences.
Number of occurrence records	208
Number of event records	209
Number of eMOF records	521
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2004-09-17 / 2004-10-29

Table 7 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT16 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise AMT16 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=amt16_coccolithophore_composition_light_microscopy_ctd_bottles
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8792
Data description	This dataset contains coccolithophore abundance data from CTD bottles collected during the AMT16 cruise in the Atlantic between Cape Town, South Africa and the United Kingdom in May-June 2005. Bottle samples were collected at six light depths (i.e. at different PAR levels) from the pre-dawn (between approximately 03:00 - 04:30 local time) and noon CTD casts. Microscope enumeration of coccolithophores and coccoliths was performed by filtering a 100 - 500 milliliters water sample through a Millipore HA filter, which was then rinsed with borate buffer, and frozen in a petri dish until counted. The filter was placed on a glass microscope slide, and a 60 degrees Celsius Canada Balsam was placed on top of the filter, followed by a cover slip. The clarified filter was examined for birefringent and plated coccolithophore counts, with an Olympus BH2 microscope equipped with polarization optics. For statistical reasons, 200 coccoliths or cells were counted from each sample, when available. These data were collected for the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project by scientists from the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences.

Number of occurrence records	548
Number of event records	339
Number of eMOF records	1,646
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2005-05-20 / 2005-06-29

Table 8 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC039 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC039 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=jc039_coccolithophore_composition_light_microscopy_ctd_bottles
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8801
Data description	This dataset contains coccolithophore abundance data from CTD bottle samples collected during the JC039 cruise in the Atlantic between Falmouth, UK and Punta Arenas, Chile in October–December 2009. Niskin samples were collected during the pre-dawn CTD (second cast of the day) from six light depths (1%, 7%, 14%, 33%, 55%, 97%) and from two deeper (down to 200 m) depths for coccolith enumeration. Coccolith and cell counts were collected on Millipore HA (nitrocellulose) filters which were rinsed with a potassium tetraborate buffer and frozen at -20° C. Samples were then dried and mounted onto slides using Norland Optical Adhesive. These were then enumerated by birefringence microscopy (Balch et al. 2011). These data were collected by scientists from the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences and contribute to the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project.
Number of occurrence records	620
Number of event records	384
Number of eMOF records	1,865
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2009-10-13 / 2009-12-01

Table 9 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC039 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (surface underway)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC039 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (surface underway)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=jc039_coccolithophore_composition_light_microscopy_surface_underway
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8795
Data description	This dataset contains coccolithophore abundance data from surface underway samples collected during the JC039 cruise in the Atlantic between Falmouth, UK and Punta Arenas, Chile from October to December 2009. Samples were collected from the non-toxic water supply three times per day, approximately every 3 to 4 hours spaced between CTD stations. Coccolith and cell counts were collected on Millipore

	HA (nitrocellulose) filters which were rinsed with a potassium tetraborate buffer and frozen at -20° C. Samples were then dried and mounted onto slides using Norland Optical Adhesive. These were then enumerated by birefringence microscopy. These data were collected by scientists from the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences and contribute to the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project.
Number of occurrence records	212
Number of event records	213
Number of eMOF records	531
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2009-10-13 / 2009-10-01

Table 10 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC053 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC053 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=jc053_coccolithophor_composition_light_microscopy_ctd_bottles
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8796
Data description	This dataset contains coccolithophore abundance data from CTD bottle samples collected during the JC053 cruise in the Atlantic between Southampton, UK and Punta Arenas, Chile in October-November 2010. Niskin samples were collected during the pre-dawn CTD (second cast of the day) from six light depths (1%, 7%, 14%, 33%, 55%, 97%). Samples for microscopic enumeration of coccolithophores and coccoliths were collected on Millipore HA (nitrocellulose) filters and rinsed with potassium tetraborate buffer, then frozen at -20° C. Samples were then dried, mounted onto slides using Norland Optical Adhesive and enumerated using by birefringent microscopy. These data were collected by scientists from the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences and contribute to the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project.
Number of occurrence records	485
Number of event records	308
Number of eMOF records	1,463
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2010-10-12 / 2010-11-25

Table 11 – Dataset summary of “Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC053 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (CTD bottles)”.

Dataset title	Atlantic Meridional Transect cruise JC053 Coccolithophore composition - light microscopy (surface underway)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=jc053_coccolithophore_composition_light_microscopy_surface_underway
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8797

Data description	This dataset contains coccolithophore abundance data from surface underway samples collected during the JC053 cruise in the Atlantic between Southampton, UK and Punta Arenas, Chile in October-November 2010. Samples were also collected four times per day from the non-toxic water supply. Samples for microscopic enumeration of coccolithophores and coccoliths were collected on Millipore HA (nitrocellulose) filters and rinsed with potassium tetraborate buffer, then frozen at -20° C. Samples were then dried, mounted onto slides using Norland Optical Adhesive and enumerated using by birefringent microscopy. These data were collected by scientists from the Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences and contribute to the Atlantic Meridional Transect (AMT) project.
Number of occurrence records	260
Number of event records	261
Number of eMOF records	651
Geographic coverage	North and South Atlantic Ocean
Temporal coverage	2010-10-12 / 2010-11-25

2.1.2.2. Marine Productivity Programme biodiversity data

Table 12 – Dataset summary of “Marine Productivity programme cruise DI258 - Microzooplankton taxonomic data (CTD and Ocean Sampler)”.

Dataset title	Marine Productivity programme cruise DI258 - Microzooplankton taxonomic data (CTD and Ocean Sampler)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1000823_di258_microzooplankton_ctd
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8802
Data description	This dataset contains microzooplankton abundance data from CTD and Ocean Sampler (OS) deployments during the Marine Productivity programme cruise DI258 to the northern North Atlantic in November - December 2001. Samples from the CTD and from all bottles of the OS were collected and preserved in 10% Lugol's iodine for microzooplankton analysis onshore. All species were placed into size categories and into taxonomic groupings. Abundance and biomass data are included.
Number of occurrence records	646
Number of event records	98
Number of eMOF records	2,652
Geographic coverage	Northern North Atlantic (Irminger Sea and parts of the Iceland Basin)
Temporal coverage	2001-11-01 / 2001-12-18

Table 13 – Dataset summary of “Marine Productivity programme cruise DI262 - Microzooplankton taxonomic data (CTD and Ocean Sampler)”.

Dataset title	Marine Productivity programme cruise DI262 - Microzooplankton taxonomic data (CTD and Ocean Sampler)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1000852_di262_microzooplankton_ctd

IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8803
Data description	This dataset contains microzooplankton abundance data from CTD and Ocean Sampler (OS) deployments during the Marine Productivity programme cruise DI262 to the northern North Atlantic in April-May 2002. Samples from the CTD and from all bottles of the OS were collected and preserved in 10% Lugol's iodine for microzooplankton analysis onshore. All species were placed into size categories and into taxonomic groupings. Abundance and biomass data are included.
Number of occurrence records	1,919
Number of event records	152
Number of eMOF records	7,842
Geographic coverage	Northern North Atlantic (Irminger Sea and parts of the Iceland Basin)
Temporal coverage	2002-04-18 / 2002-05-27

Table 14 – Dataset summary of “Marine Productivity programme cruise DI264 - Microzooplankton taxonomic data (CTD and Ocean Sampler)”.

Dataset title	Marine Productivity programme cruise DI264 - Microzooplankton taxonomic data (CTD and Ocean Sampler)
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1000890_di264_microzooplankton_ctd
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8798
Data description	This dataset contains microzooplankton abundance data from CTD and Ocean Sampler (OS) deployments during the Marine Productivity programme cruise DI264 to the northern North Atlantic in July - August 2002. Samples from the CTD and from all bottles of the OS were collected and preserved in 10% Lugol's iodine for microzooplankton analysis onshore. All species were placed into size categories and into taxonomic groupings. Abundance and biomass data are included.
Number of occurrence records	1,100
Number of event records	103
Number of eMOF records	4,522
Geographic coverage	Northern North Atlantic (Irminger Sea and parts of the Iceland Basin)
Temporal coverage	2002-07-25 / 2002-08-28

2.1.2.3. Plymouth Marine Laboratory Bristol Channel Project biodiversity data

Table 15 – Dataset summary of “The Plymouth Marine Laboratory Bristol Channel Project - Zooplankton and fish taxonomy and abundance”.

Dataset title	The Plymouth Marine Laboratory Bristol Channel Project - Zooplankton and fish taxonomy and abundance
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1032302_bristol_channel_zooplankton
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8799
Data description	The dataset comprises plankton and fish abundance data, as well as fish length data. The data were collected from the Bristol Channel, Severn Estuary, Celtic Sea and Plymouth Sound between 1971 and 1978. Measurements were taken over a series

	of 50 cruises. The most intensive sampling took place before 1975. The original data were collated and stored at Institute for Marine Environmental Research (IMER), which became Plymouth Marine Laboratory in 1988. As this is a large and important data set, which was previously held in an inaccessible format, it was selected for long-term archival at BODC as part of the NERC SEEDCORN programme.
Number of occurrence records	43,652
Number of event records	3,628
Number of eMOF records	118,577
Geographic coverage	The Bristol Channel
Temporal coverage	1971-07-27 / 1978-01-25

2.1.2.4. PROcesses of Vertical Exchange in Shelf Seas (PROV ESS) biodiversity data

Table 16 – Dataset summary of “PROcesses of Vertical Exchange in Shelf Seas cruise D1198 - Meso-zooplankton abundance data”.

Dataset title	PROcesses of Vertical Exchange in Shelf Seas cruise D1198 - Meso-zooplankton abundance data
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/bodc/resource?r=1033178_d1198_meso-zooplankton
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8800
Data description	This dataset contains zooplankton abundance data collected during the RV Dana D1198 cruise in the Northern North Sea, in October 1998. Zooplankton samples were collected using an <i>in situ</i> underwater plankton pump through a 30 µm mesh. The pump was deployed up to 4 times daily and at eight depths (5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60 and 80 m) with a pumping time of 3 to 5 minutes in each layer. The nets were carefully washed down, and the contents of the cod ends filtered through a 40 µm mesh. Samples were then preserved in 4% borax buffered formalin in sea water for future analysis. These data were collected for the PROcesses of Vertical Exchange in Shelf Seas (PROV ESS) project by scientists from the Danish Institute for Fisheries Research (DIFRES). The originator format data are available from: https://www.bodc.ac.uk/data/published_data_library/catalogue/10.5285/2bd1b010-66a1-3dc1-e063-7086abc08ac3
Number of occurrence records	5,730
Number of event records	196
Number of eMOF records	18,851
Geographic coverage	Northern North Sea
Temporal coverage	1998-10-14 / 1998-10-26

2.1.3. Discussion

During the project, a comprehensive mapping between the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) database and the Darwin Core standard was created. A script was developed to automatically generate Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A) format files from datasets held in the BODC database, streamlining the process, and reducing manual effort. BODC decided to align the dataset granularity with their internal data tracking system which typically separates datasets by project, research expedition, data type and originator. Hence, this means that new data will be submitted as new

datasets rather than added to existing dataset(s). In conclusion, a semi-automated pipeline was set up and a total of 15 datasets have been submitted with this pipeline so far. BODC stated in their final report that many more datasets will be published in the months to come, contributing valuable data to the global research community.

2.2. Futurismo: linking whale watching tourism with cetacean research in the Azores.

2.2.1. General information

Table 17 – General information on “Futurismo: linking whale watching tourism with cetacean research in the Azores”.

Organisation	Futurismo Azores Adventures
Data description	Cetacean sightings by Futurismo (whale-watching tourism) in the Azores
Budget	€53,400

2.2.2. Datasets

Table 18 – Dataset summary of “Whale-Watching cetacean occurrences by Futurismo Azores Adventures from 2008 to 2018 off São Miguel (Azores)”.

Dataset title	Whale-Watching cetacean occurrences by Futurismo Azores Adventures from 2008 to 2018 off São Miguel (Azores)
IPT resource URL	http://ipt.gbif.pt/ipt/resource?r=futurismo_sm_0818
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8804
Data description	Whale-watching vessels have become valuable platforms for cetacean data collection worldwide. In the Azores, a cetacean hotspot in the Atlantic, Futurismo Azores Adventures, a family-owned tourism company with whale-watching as its core business, has been collecting data regularly since 2008. The current dataset compiles observations of 20 cetacean species and 19 other species of marine megafauna, recorded by Futurismo Azores Adventures off São Miguel Island (Azores, Portugal) from 2008 to 2018. Data was collected during 4,219 whale-watching commercial trips conducted daily and year-round. This information has been prepared for publication within the framework of the DTO-BioFlow project, which aims to enable a data flow into the EU Digital Twin Ocean.
Number of occurrence records	20,413
Number of event records	18,425
Number of eMOF records	88,317
Geographic coverage	Data was collected off São Miguel Island, one of the easternmost islands of the Archipelago of the Azores in the Mid-Atlantic.
Temporal coverage	2008-05-01 / 2018-12-31

2.2.3. Discussion

During the project, Futurismo’s data collection methodology was updated to maximise data value and simplify standardisation and transformation of data to Darwin Core (DwC) in the future. Moreover, Futurismo will periodically

hold training sessions to keep the team informed and up-to-date on the best practices for data gathering. After data compilation and thorough data control, the data gathered from 2008 to 2018 was published on an Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT) instance. The methodology used to collect and store the data was changed in 2019, which is why the data from 2019 to 2024 was not yet published, but Futurismo aims to publish this in the future. The methodology since then has largely remained the same, so automated procedures will be used to transform the data to DwC, supporting the goal of maintaining yearly updates and ensuring the continuity of the DTO-BioFlow initiative.

2.3. Plankton Imaging Data Flow: Establishing a European data flow for phyto- and microzooplankton data from automated AI-assisted imaging in flow analyses

2.3.1. General information

Table 19 – General information on “Plankton Imaging Data Flow: Establishing a European data flow for phyto- and microzooplankton data from automated AI-assisted imaging in flow analyses”.

Organisation	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
Data description	Phyto- and microzooplankton data from Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB) in European waters
Budget	€52,900

2.3.2. Datasets

Table 20 – Dataset summary on “SHARK - Phyto- and Microzooplankton Data Collected by Imaging FlowCytobots (IFCB) in Swedish and Adjacent Waters”.

Dataset title	SHARK - Phyto- and Microzooplankton Data Collected by Imaging FlowCytobots (IFCB) in Swedish and Adjacent Waters
IPT resource URL	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=shark-planktonimaging
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8805
Data description	Data is stored in the Swedish Ocean Archive database (SHARK), by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), National Oceanographic Data Centre. Monitoring is performed by Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute. The monitoring is financed by specific projects. In short, analysis of phyto- and microzooplankton species composition, abundance and biomass is carried out for the following purposes: (i) to describe temporal trends as well as the intensity and occurrence of blooms; (ii) to describe the spatial distribution of species; (iii) to identify key species (e.g. dominating, harmful, potential non-indigenous and/or invasive species, as well as indicator species); (iv) to provide basic data for complex ecosystem analyses, food web studies, modelling as well as for requirements in the frame of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive of the European Union (MSFD European Union, 2008) and the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD European Union, 2000). In this dataset data from Tangesund oceanographic platform, Swedish Skagerrak coast year 2016 (IFCB110), and from R/V Svea (https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C17/current/77SE/) from year 2022 onwards

	(IFCB134) can be found. Other sampling platforms are possible to be added in the future.
Number of occurrence records	121,103
Number of event records	17,731
Number of eMOF records	1,111,062
Geographic coverage	Baltic Sea
Temporal coverage	2016-08-10 / 2024-12-15

2.3.3. Discussion

During the project, a semi-automated pipeline was set up, which consists of the following steps from data processing to data publication:

1. Blob and feature extraction through IFCB-analysis (fully automated on SMHI server);
2. Random forest image classification through IFCB-analysis (fully automated on SMHI server);
3. Summarize data and metadata by running IFCB-data-pipeline for the selected year using *iRfcb*;
4. Import summarized data into the SHARK database;
5. Transform the SHARK zip-archive into a DwC-A and upload to GBIF Sweden IPT.

All procedures for updating the dataset are documented on GitHub under the following repositories:

- <https://github.com/hsosik/ifcb-analysis>
- <https://github.com/nodc-sweden/ifcb-data-pipeline>
- <https://github.com/sharkdata/darwincore>
- <https://github.com/EuropeanIFCBGroup/iRfcb>

The SMHI IFCB dataset will be updated on an annual to bi-annual basis. The project also provided effort towards presenting and sharing these pipelines with the European IFCB network (through presentations and user-friendly [tutorials](#)) and has also planned a data workshop past the end of the project to assist Norwegian colleagues to set up an IFCB data-sharing workflow. The Swedish NODC is now prepared to receive and publish plankton imaging data from other sources, so additional plankton imaging datasets could also be expected flow to EMODnet Biology through the pipelines established in this project.

2.4. Strandaanspoelsel (beach washup) Monitoring Project (SMP)

2.4.1. General information

Table 21 – General information on “Strandaanspoelsel (beach washup) Monitoring Project (SMP)”.

Organisation	Stichting ANEMOON (Netherlands), foundation, NGO
Data description	Biodiversity data collected along the Dutch shoreline in the framework of the Strandaanspoelsel Monitoring Project (SMP)
Budget	€53,300

2.4.2. Datasets

Table 22 – Dataset summary of “ANEMOON Beach washup monitoring (SMP) data along the Dutch coastline collected through citizen science”.

Dataset title	ANEMOON Beach washup monitoring (SMP) data along the Dutch coastline collected through citizen science.
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.nl/bif.nl/resource?r=anemoon_smp_1977_2024
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8806
Data description	The SMP data originates from the Strandaanspoelsel (beach washup) Monitoring Project (SMP), a citizen science project executed by Stichting ANEMOON. Data dates back to 1977 and new data will keep on being added as long as there are sufficient citizen scientists. The data is from eight locations scattered along the Dutch coastline. On these locations, all washed-up marine organisms and remains are determined and counted on a biweekly or monthly basis. Macroalgae, Cnidarians, Gastropods, Cephalopods, Bivalves, Crustaceans, Echinoderms, Shark and Ray egg capsules and Bryozoans are noted at species level.
Number of occurrence records	1,625,592
Number of event records	5,028
Number of eMOF records	2,833,955
Geographic coverage	Locations scattered across the Dutch coastline.
Temporal coverage	1977-11-05 / 2021-12-24

2.4.3. Discussion

A semi-automated procedure was established during the project, which includes scripts to clean the data and to transform it to DarwinCore data files (an event table (core), an occurrence table, and an eMOF table). The data files are then used to update the dataset on the IPT. The dataset will be updated on a yearly basis. The procedure is documented and the procedure and scripts are shared internally within Stichting ANEMOON.

2.5. Management and publication of Marine Characterisation Research Project data

2.5.1. General information

Table 23 – General information on “Management and publication of Marine Characterisation Research Project data”.

Organisation	Menter Môn, UK
Data description	Biodiversity data collected in the framework of the Marine Characterisation Research Project through a variety of methods, such as passive acoustic monitoring, sonar cameras, RGB and infrared cameras, acoustic deterrent devices (ADDs), drone and boat-based observations, seal and seabird tagging and shore-based population counts.
Budget	Planned: €58,125.15 Spent: €29,062.58

2.5.2. Discussion

The Marine Characterisation Research Project (MCRP) team failed to deliver datasets, mainly due to staff shortages (due to maternity leave & long-term sickness). Due to not having enough available personnel to perform the work, the MCRP team tried to hire a third party to perform the work instead but failed to receive a quotation. It was assessed shortly after the time of the second interim report that it would not be feasible to deliver within the deadlines set within the contract, nor with an extension of a few months. Hence the contract was terminated.

2.6. Managing and publishing biodiversity data from Nord University

2.6.1. General information

Table 24 – General information on “Managing and publishing biodiversity data from Nord University”.

Organisation	Faculty of Biosciences and Aquaculture, Nord University
Data description	Biodiversity data from Nord University, such as data from zooplankton trawls, benthos grabs and undersea videos.
Budget	€25,500

2.6.2. Datasets

Table 25 – Dataset summary on “Plankton net data from subarctic fjords in the Norwegian Sea 1980-2005”.

Dataset title	Plankton net data from subarctic fjords in the Norwegian Sea 1980-2005
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.gbif.no/resource?r=longterm_zooplankton_series_nord
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8816
Data description	This data represents the data collected in the long-term zooplankton time series by Nord University. The focus is on meso-zooplankton and the slowest of the small macro-zooplankton species. Particularly the species that accounted for the biomass and major trophic positions on low levels in the planktonic food web. Priority was given to count the dominant herbivores and dominant predators.
Number of occurrence records	3,455
Number of event records	1,364
Number of eMOF records	9,459
Geographic coverage	Norwegian Sea
Temporal coverage	1980-01-17 / 2005-10-27

Table 26 – Dataset summary on, “Grab samples data from subarctic fjords in the Norwegian Sea 2013-2015”.

Dataset title	Grab samples data from subarctic fjords in the Norwegian Sea 2013-2015
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.gbif.no/resource?r=benthos_subarctic_fjords_norway
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8814

Data description	Macro-benthic dataset for three fjords in Nordland, Northern Norway: Saltfjord, Skjerstadjord and Sørfolda. At each sampling station (36 stations total), two Van Veen grab (0.1 m ²) samples were taken, sieved on a 1 mm mesh, and fixed with 4% buffered formaldehyde. The sorted individuals were identified to the lowest taxon possible (usually species level) and transferred to 70% ethanol. For each taxon, numbers, ind/0.1 m ² , and biomass, mg/0.1 m ² , are presented. The samples are stored at Nord University (Bodø, Norway)
Number of occurrence records	25,200
Number of event records	144
Number of eMOF records	25,746
Geographic coverage	Norwegian Sea
Temporal coverage	2013-04-30 / 2015-05-20

2.6.3. Discussion

As part of the project, two R scripts were developed to clean the existing zooplankton and benthos time-series datasets and sort them into Darwin Core standards, and both datasets have been published into the Norwegian GBIF IPT instance. A pipeline was created to support publication of any marine ecology sampling carried out by NORD university, and consists of (1) a web portal that gathers metadata during sampling events, (2) a guideline for the data collectors on data collection, storage and publishing, and (3) the R script used to clean the benthos time-series, though it is still not fully generalised and needs to be adapted to each situation. In addition, the people from Nord University who participated in the DTO-BioFlow data training workshop organized a seminar for the Faculty of Biosciences and Aquaculture, Nord University, to explain the importance of using Darwin Core, as well as FAIR data principles. Along with the seminar, a Darwin Core data collection template was created and distributed. Guidelines for data collection and data structure have as well been created for use at the Faculty of Biosciences and Aquaculture, Nord University. As a last step in the implementation of the new sampling procedure, a handful of staff members were picked to go through a three-hour field course, showing how to use the website (<https://fbaecodat.com/>) while sampling.

2.7. KAIROS - Zooplankton data from Arctic marine time-series to understand biodiversity dynamics

2.7.1. General information

Table 27 – General information on “KAIROS - Zooplankton data from Arctic marine time-series to understand biodiversity dynamics”.

Organisation	National Research Council, Institute of Polar Sciences (CNR-ISP) + National Research Council, Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems (CNRIRET)
Data description	Zooplankton biodiversity data from sediment traps in Svalbard collected in the framework of the Italian Arctic Marine Observing System
Budget	€59,281

2.7.2. Datasets

Table 28 – Dataset summary of “Composition and morpho-functional traits of zooplankton swimmers and sinkers collected by “Mooring Dirigibile Italia” sediment trap”.

Dataset title	Composition and morpho-functional traits of zooplankton swimmers and sinkers collected by “Mooring Dirigibile Italia” sediment trap
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/cnr-isp/resource?r=kairos_dto_bioflow
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8807
Data description	This dataset comprises zooplankton samples collected using sediment traps deployed at a depth of 87 meters at the “Mooring Dirigibile Italia” (MDI) site (78°54.815 N, 12°14.899 E) in the inner part of Kongsfjorden (Svalbard), near tidewater glacier fronts. As part of the KAIROS project, the dataset spans eight years (2014–2022) and has been curated to adhere to FAIR principles. The dataset underwent thorough data review, formatting, quality control, validation, and standardization. Furthermore, zooplankton data was integrated with oceanographic data (seawater temperature and salinity) collected synoptically at the same site. Morpho-functional traits for the different taxa collected were also measured for campaign VIII and XIII to better characterize the zooplankton size structures.
Number of occurrence records	1,674
Number of event records	101
Number of eMOF records	6,370
Geographic coverage	Kongsfjorden, Svalbard
Temporal coverage	2014-09-12 / 2022-08-16

2.7.3. Discussion

A workflow for data standardization was developed to ensure sustained updates of the KAIROS dataset. Well-documented R scripts are used to automate the cleaning, filtering, and formatting of datasets. The R scripts were made available on a restricted-access GitHub repository to ensure transparency and reproducibility. New datasets will be published annually, incorporating the latest collected data.

2.8. Integration of southeastern Mediterranean long-term biodiversity data into EU-DTO

2.8.1. General information

Table 29 – General information on “Integration of southeastern Mediterranean long-term biodiversity data into EU-DTO”.

Organisation	Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research (IOLR), government research institute
Data description	Southeastern Mediterranean biodiversity data, collated in the ISRAMARBIO database
Budget	€60,000

2.8.2. Datasets

Table 30 – Dataset summary on “Cambridge expedition to the Suez Canal 1924”.

Dataset title	Cambridge expedition to the Suez Canal 1924
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/iolr/resource?r=cambridge_expedition_to_the_suez_canal_1924
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8808
Data description	This dataset was the result of a collection expedition in the Suez Canal and its adjacent Mediterranean Sea and Red Sea. The expedition was organized by the Cambridge University and was held between September and December 1924.
Number of occurrence records	2,201
Number of event records	92
Number of eMOF records	2,293
Geographic coverage	Suez Canal
Temporal coverage	1920-01-09 / 1924-12-29

Table 31 – Dataset summary on “Macrofauna of the eastern Mediterranean Israeli shallow shelf-2005-2022”.

Dataset title	Macrofauna of the eastern Mediterranean Israeli shallow shelf-2005-2022
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/iolr/resource?r=iolr_macrofauna_of_the_Israeli_shallow_shelf-2005-2022
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8809
Data description	The records in this dataset were and will be derived from past and ongoing infauna monitoring efforts in the Israeli waters at depths from 5-2000 m performed by the Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research, a governmental marine research institute.
Number of occurrence records	20,166
Number of event records	585
Number of eMOF records	21,921
Geographic coverage	Israeli Exclusive Economic Zone
Temporal coverage	2005-07-20 / 2022-07-25

Table 32 – Dataset summary on “Macrofauna of the eastern Mediterranean Israeli shelf”.

Dataset title	Macrofauna of the eastern Mediterranean Israeli shelf
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/iolr/resource?r=macrofauna_of_the_eastern_mediterranean_Israeli_shelf
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&david=8810
Data description	The records in this dataset were and will be derived from past and ongoing infauna monitoring efforts in the Israeli continental shelf at depths from 5-100 m performed by the Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research, a governmental marine research institute.

Number of occurrence records	71,238
Number of event records	2,236
Number of eMOF records	77,946
Geographic coverage	Israeli Exclusive Economic Zone
Temporal coverage	2004-05-18 / 2023-05-01

Table 33 – Dataset summary on “Macrofauna of the Israeli eastern Mediterranean 36-1420m-2013-2023”.

Dataset title	Macrofauna of the Israeli eastern Mediterranean 36-1420m-2013-2023
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/iolr/resource?r=iolr_mediterranean_israeli_fauna
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8811
Data description	The records in this dataset were and will be derived from past and ongoing infauna monitoring efforts in the Israeli waters at depths from 31-2000 m performed by the Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research, a governmental marine research institute.
Number of occurrence records	8,198
Number of event records	425
Number of eMOF records	9,473
Geographic coverage	Israeli Exclusive Economic Zone
Temporal coverage	2013-06-16 / 2023-02-15

Table 34 – Dataset summary on “Shelf Haifa Bay Israel Mediterranean Epibenthic communities 1974-1975”.

Dataset title	Shelf Haifa Bay Israel Mediterranean Epibenthic communities 1974-1975
IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/iolr/resource?r=aaa
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8812
Data description	The records in this dataset were derived from a MSc thesis (in Hebrew) cited: Tom M 1976, the Benthic associations of Haifa Bay, submitted to the University of Tel Aviv, 117 pp., available from the University library and described also in: Tom M and Galil BS 1991. The faunal associations of Haifa Bay, Mediterranean coast of Israel. P.S.Z.N.I. Mar Ecol 12: 75-86, https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0485.1991.tb00085.x
Number of occurrence records	1,400
Number of event records	21
Number of eMOF records	1,463
Geographic coverage	Israeli Exclusive Economic Zone
Temporal coverage	1974-04-15 / 1975-09-17

Table 35 – Dataset summary on “Sponges of the Israeli Mediterranean waters”.

Dataset title	Sponges of the Israeli Mediterranean waters
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IPT resource URL	https://ipt.vliz.be/iolr/resource?r=sponges_of_the_israeli_mediterranean_waters
IMIS metadata record URL	https://vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&daside=8813
Data description	This dataset contains observations extracted from a variety of scientific articles and reports regarding the sponges inhabiting rocky substrates along the shelf of Israeli waters between 1962-2018.
Number of occurrence records	1,179
Number of event records	33
Number of eMOF records	1,212
Geographic coverage	Israeli Exclusive Economic Zone
Temporal coverage	1962-01-01 / 2018-03-01

2.8.3. Discussion

Since the ISRMARBIO database contains data from various sources, the data is published as several different datasets. Six datasets were published during the project. Publication/updating of datasets will continue past the end of the project. Infaunal monitoring done by IOLR will be published annually. Other projects will be deposited upon their availability.

2.9. Marine Megafauna Data for EU Digital Twin Ocean

2.9.1. General information

Table 36 – General information on “Marine Megafauna Data for EU Digital Twin Ocean”.

Organisation	Bangor University & Sea Watch Foundation
Data description	Marine megafauna sightings in European seas collected by the UK Sea Watch Foundation (SWF) and its partners.
Budget	€ 57,518

2.9.2. Datasets

Table 37 – Dataset summary.

Dataset title	Sea Watch Foundation Marine Megafauna Sightings (1930 to 1970): batch_1
IPT resource URL	https://www.dassh.ac.uk/ipt/resource?r=seawatchfoundation_marine_megafauna_sightings_1930_to_1970
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&daside=8817
Data description	The Sea Watch Foundation has been collecting both effort-based and non-effort-based sightings data of marine mammals and other megafauna since the late 1960s. The main area of coverage is the waters around Britain and Ireland but with some surveys elsewhere. Data come from platforms ranging from small to large vessels either on dedicated survey or platforms of opportunity, and from coastal land sites. Data collected include environmental conditions, marine traffic, and seabird

	associations. Sighting records come from all types of marine users, from marine mammal biologists to citizen scientists and members of the public. All sightings are checked, and species ID validated from still or video images and/or descriptions, except in those cases where persons are known, experienced, observers.
Number of occurrence records	743
Number of event records	739
Number of eMOF records	5,745
Geographic coverage	Mainly waters around Britain and Ireland
Temporal coverage	1931-06-05 / 1970-12-31

Table 38 – Dataset summary.

Dataset title	Sea Watch Foundation Marine Megafauna Sightings: 1971 to present
IPT resource URL	https://www.dassh.ac.uk/ipt/resource?r=seawatchfoundation_marine_megafauna_sightings_1971_to_present
IMIS metadata record URL	https://www.vliz.be/nl/imis?module=dataset&daside=8818
Data description	The Sea Watch Foundation has been collecting both effort-based and non-effort-based sightings data of marine mammals and other megafauna since the late 1960s. The main area of coverage is the waters around Britain and Ireland but with some surveys elsewhere. Data come from platforms ranging from small to large vessels either on dedicated survey or platforms of opportunity, and from coastal land sites. Data collected include environmental conditions, marine traffic, and seabird associations. Sighting records come from all types of marine users, from marine mammal biologists to citizen scientists and members of the public. All sightings are checked, and species ID validated from still or video images and/or descriptions, except in those cases where persons are known, experienced, observers.
Number of occurrence records	232,694
Number of event records	196,822
Number of eMOF records	1,785,721
Geographic coverage	Mainly waters around Britain and Ireland
Temporal coverage	1971-02-20 / 2024-12-30

2.9.3. Discussion

The majority of historical datasets, spanning from the 1930s (but mainly from the 1970s) to the present and previously stored in various file formats, were successfully integrated into a unified database management system. A comprehensive quality assurance process was conducted, ensuring that most of the valid data relevant to the project was thoroughly checked, processed, and published. Additionally, a system was developed to streamline data extraction, producing Darwin Core Archives in an automated way from the database, enabling efficient publishing and updating of the dataset(s). The dataset(s) will be updated annually.

3. Conclusions

A total of 29 datasets were published within the scope of the nine selected projects which were awarded a FSTP grant in this first round of the DTO-BioFlow open calls organized within Task 2.5. These datasets combined represent a total of more than two million occurrence records. The datasets cover a wide array of methods such as citizen science observations, AI-assisted imaging and net trawling, focusing on a variety of organisms, from cetaceans to plankton, being collected from different regions, ranging from the Arctic Ocean to the Mediterranean Sea to the Azores and the South Atlantic Ocean. In addition, the datasets cover a wide temporal range, from 1920 to 2024. Twelve datasets span more than five years, seven span more than ten, and two span more than 50, providing a nice set of long-term monitoring datasets. All datasets have been published on IPT instances, from where they have been/ are being/ will be picked up by data aggregators, i.e. GBIF, OBIS and EMODnet Biology. Through EMODnet Biology they will soon reach the DTO (expected in May 2025). Thanks to the (in most cases semi-automated) procedures established during these projects, this number of datasets and number of occurrence records is expected to continue growing in the future, generating a sustained data flow towards the DTO.

